

1 **Fully aerobic bioscrubber for the desulfurization**
2 **of H₂S-rich biogas**

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16 **Abstract**

17 A fully aerobic bioscrubber for the desulfurization of H₂S-rich biogas was developed in
18 the present study by coupling an absorption column and a bubble column bioreactor.
19 The bioscrubber treated H₂S loading rates of 37, 59, and 100 g S m_{liquid}⁻³ h⁻¹ at gas
20 residence times of 6.6, 4.1 and 2.4 min in the absorption column, respectively. Stable
21 H₂S removal efficiencies above 80% were recorded at all the conditions tested. The
22 bioscrubber was robust towards short- and long-term operation shutdowns (5 and 18
23 days), the H₂S removal performance being recovered after few hours. The aerated
24 bubble column bioreactor was operated at slightly alkaline conditions (pH 8 ± 0.5),
25 which prevented H₂S stripping and allowed sulfur oxidation performances higher than
26 75% regardless of the operating conditions tested. Bacterial community characterization
27 by 16S rRNA pyrosequencing revealed that the operating conditions (slightly alkaline
28 pH, sulfate concentrations of up to 25,000 g m⁻³ and dilution rates of 5.7×10⁻³– 8.6×10⁻³
29 h⁻¹) shaped a specialized community highly efficient for H₂S oxidation. Three
30 *Proteobacteria* were predominant in the bubble column bioreactor, namely
31 *Thioalkalimicrobium cyclicum*, *Stappia* sp and *Ochrobactrum* sp with relative
32 abundances of 68.18, 13.49 and 7.61%, respectively.

33

34 **Keywords:** Biological desulfurization; fully aerobic conditions; H₂S-rich biogas; two-
35 stage bioscrubber; renewable energy.

36 Nomenclature

GRT	Gas retention time in the absorption column (min)
ORP	Oxidation reduction potential (mV)
OUR	Oxygen uptake rate ($\text{g O}_2 \text{ m}_{\text{liquid}}^{-3} \text{ h}$)
Q_{Air}	Volumetric flow rate of air ($\text{m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$)
Q_{Biogas}	Volumetric flow rate of biogas ($\text{m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$)
RE	S-H ₂ S removal efficiency (%)
SEC	S-H ₂ S elimination capacity ($\text{g S m}_{\text{liquid}}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$)
SER	Sulfur emission rate ($\text{g S m}_{\text{liquid}}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$)
SIL	Sulfur inlet load ($\text{g S m}_{\text{liquid}}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$)
SOP	Sulfur oxidation performance (%)
SS	Suspended solids (g m^{-3})
$[\text{S-H}_2\text{S}]_{\text{Gas, inlet}}^{\text{Column}}$	S-H ₂ S concentration at the inlet of the absorption column (g S m^{-3})
$[\text{S-H}_2\text{S}]_{\text{Gas, outlet}}^{\text{Column}}$	S-H ₂ S concentration at the outlet of the absorption column (g S m^{-3})
$[\text{S-H}_2\text{S}]_{\text{Gas, outlet}}^{\text{Bubble column reactor}}$	S-H ₂ S concentration at the outlet of the bubble column reactor (g S m^{-3})
V_{Liquid}	Volume of liquid in the bubble column reactor (m^3)
VSS	Volatile suspended solids (g m^{-3})

37

38 1. Introduction

39 Biogas, mainly composed of ~60-65% CH₄ and ~35-40% CO₂ is a renewable fuel
 40 obtained from the anaerobic degradation of organic matter [1]. Depending on the
 41 characteristics of the organic matter, biogas may contain a sort of pollutants that must
 42 be removed prior its use in engines or turbines to produce heat and power [2]. H₂S is
 43 one of the most common biogas pollutants, which causes corrosion to internal
 44 combustion devices and industrial pipes [3]. H₂S is also toxic for humans, being lethal
 45 at a concentration of 300 ppm_v (0.03% v/v) [4]. The biogas generated from sulfur-rich
 46 effluents (e.g. wastewaters from pulp and paper mills, citric acid production,
 47 sugar/ethanol production from molasses, edible oil industry refineries, wine production
 48 and intensive pig farms) typically contains H₂S concentrations between 2,000 and
 49 20,000 ppm_v (0.2–2.0 % v/v) [5–7]. However, the maximum H₂S concentration

50 acceptable in combined heat and power engines is in the range of 100 - 500 ppm_v [4].
51 Therefore, H₂S-rich biogas must be desulfurized before its use for heat and power
52 generation.

53

54 Physical-chemical technologies for biogas desulfurization such as adsorption on
55 activated carbon, chemical scrubbing or thermal decomposition are costly and generate
56 secondary pollution [8,9]. Chemical scrubbing, a common purification technology for
57 H₂S-rich biogas, requires large volumes of alkaline water that must be subsequently
58 treated [10]. Alternative technologies based on the activity of sulfur-oxidizing bacteria
59 are also available even at industrial scale. This is the case of the commercial
60 THIOPAQ[®] process, which is a reference technology for biogas desulfurization at
61 industrial scale (as well as its variation SHELL-PAQUES[®] developed for purification of
62 natural gas under pressure) [11,12]. In this technology, H₂S is absorbed in a scrubber
63 under alkaline conditions ($\text{H}_2\text{S} + \text{OH}^- \rightarrow \text{HS}^- + \text{H}_2\text{O}$). Then, the absorbed HS⁻ is
64 partially oxidized to elemental sulfur (S⁰) by chemolithoautotrophic bacteria in an
65 aerated bioreactor ($\text{HS}^- + 0.5 \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{S}^0 + \text{OH}^-$). There are also commercial
66 desulfurization technologies based on biotrickling filtration that target the full H₂S
67 oxidation to sulfate [13–15]. This is the case of the Sulphus[®] and SOX[®] technologies
68 developed by Pure Air Solutions and Aeris, respectively [16,17]. Fertilizer production is
69 a main application of the sulfur recovered during biogas desulfurization [18,19]. Since
70 SO₄²⁻ is the chemical form taken up by plants, the liquid stream leaving the
71 desulfurization system might be valorized as liquid fertilizer after adding adequate
72 proportions of other nutrients (e.g. N, P or K) [11,20]. Hence, the production of sulfate
73 rather than S⁰ could be in some instances more convenient [21].

74

75 In biotrickling filters the H₂S absorption and biological oxidation occur in the same unit.
76 The absorbed HS⁻ is oxidized by chemolithoautotrophic bacteria adhered on a packed
77 bed under aerobic conditions (HS⁻ + 2O₂ → SO₄²⁻ + H⁺) [6,13–15] However, a critical
78 operating issue in biotrickling filters treating H₂S-rich biogas is the frequent clogging of
79 the packed bed due to accumulation of elemental sulfur [9,14,21,22]. Bed clogging
80 comes from supplying less O₂ than that required to achieve the full oxidation of H₂S to
81 SO₄²⁻ (2 moles of O₂ per mole of H₂S). On the contrary, biogas dilution is likely to
82 occur in biotrickling filters operated with excess of O₂ supply [9,14,22,23]. Therefore,
83 fully aerobic biological technologies must still be improved for the efficient and robust
84 desulfurization of H₂S-rich biogas.

85

86 The performance of a fully aerobic two-stage bioscrubber for the aerobic desulfurization
87 of H₂S-rich biogas was investigated in the present study. In this configuration air and
88 biogas do not mix, which avoids biogas dilution, while allowing the full oxygenation of
89 the liquid phase to prevent elemental sulfur accumulation. The scrubber was operated
90 under slightly alkaline pH conditions to prevent H₂S stripping from the aerated liquid
91 phase. The desulfurization performance was evaluated in terms of S-H₂S removal
92 efficiency, S-H₂S elimination capacity and the percentage of S-H₂S consumed that was
93 fully oxidized to S-SO₄²⁻. The bacterial communities established after 80 days of
94 operation were also characterized by 16S rRNA pyrosequencing.

95

96 **2. Materials and methods**

97 **2.1. Chemicals and mineral salt medium**

98 All chemicals for mineral salt medium (MSM) preparation were purchased from VWR
99 with a purity of at least 99%. MSM (final pH, 8.5) used for operating the desulfurization

100 system contained (g L^{-1}): NaHCO_3 3.50, NH_4Cl 1.00, K_2HPO_4 0.15, KH_2PO_4 0.12,
101 $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 0.2 and CaCl_2 0.02, along with 1 mL/L_{MSM} of a trace element solution (g
102 L^{-1} : H_3BO_3 2.86, $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 0.22, $\text{MnCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 1.4, $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ 0.01,
103 $\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 0.39). A stock solution of NaHCO_3 (75 g L^{-1}) was used for pH control.
104 Synthetic biogas (0.5% H_2S in N_2) was purchased from Air Liquide (Spain).

105

106 **2.2. Experimental setup**

107 The desulfurization system consisted in an absorption column of 600 mL (5 cm inner
108 diameter, 300 mm height) coupled with a bubble column reactor of 1,100 mL (6 cm
109 inner diameter, 400 mm height). The bubble column reactor was operated at a working
110 volume of 970 mL. Biogas containing 5,000 ppm_v of H_2S was fed at the bottom of the
111 absorption column at flow rates from 0.091 to 0.247 L min^{-1} , yielding gas residence
112 times (GRT) in the absorption column from 6.6 to 2.4 min (Fig. 1). The liquid phase
113 was recirculated counter-currently relative the biogas in the absorption column at
114 velocities of 2.5 and 3.7 m h^{-1} with a peristaltic pump (Watson Marlow, USA). The air
115 stream (compressed, filtered and dried) was introduced at the bottom of the bubble
116 column reactor through a porous steel sparger at a volumetric biogas/air ratio of 1:1.
117 The gas flow rates were controlled by calibrated rotameters (ColePalmer, Illinois,
118 USA). The operational conditions are summarized in Table 1. The bubble column
119 reactor was provided with a calibrated pH probe, which was connected to a LabQuest[®]
120 data acquisition card (Vernier, Oregon, USA). The pH of the liquid phase was
121 controlled at a value of 8.0 ± 0.5 using a digital control unit (Vernier, Oregon, USA)
122 linking the data acquisition card with a peristaltic pump (Watson Marlow) dosing the
123 stock solution of NaHCO_3 . The NaHCO_3 addition served for pH control and inorganic
124 carbon supply for the growth the autotrophic sulfur oxidizing microorganisms.

125 <Table 1>

126 <Figure 1>

127

128 From day 3 on, the following protocol for exchanging culture broth by fresh MSM was
129 set in the bubble column reactor to avoid nutrients limitations and excessive
130 accumulation of sulfate: Monday - Thursday, 200 mL each day; Friday, 400 mL (no
131 liquid renewal in Saturday and Sunday). These liquid exchanges corresponded with
132 dilution rates in the bubble column reactor of 5.7×10^{-3} – 8.6×10^{-3} h⁻¹. Biogas
133 composition at the outlet of the absorption column and at the outlet of the bubble
134 column reactor was periodically monitored (before liquid phase renewal). The
135 concentration of S-SO₄²⁻, S²⁻, inorganic carbon, suspended solids (SS) and volatile
136 suspended solids (VSS) in the liquid phase were periodically measured as well as the
137 dissolved oxygen concentration, the redox potential (ORP) and conductivity. The
138 bubble column reactor was inoculated with 10% v/v of a secondary activated sludge
139 from a municipal wastewater treatment plant (Valencia, Spain). The desulfurization
140 system was operated at room temperature (21.0 ± 1.5 °C).

141

142 **2.3. S-H₂S removal performance parameters**

143 The following parameters were used to evaluate the performance of the desulfurization
144 system, which were based on the working volume of the bubble column reactor. Both
145 the S-H₂S removal efficiency and the elimination capacity considered potential S-H₂S
146 stripping from the bubble bioreactor due to aeration.

147

148 Sulfur inlet load (SIL):

149
$$SIL = [S-H_2S]_{Gas, inlet}^{Column} \times \frac{Q_{Biogas}}{V_{Liquid}} \quad (1)$$

150

151 Sulfur emission rate from the desulfurization system (SER):

152
$$SER = [S-H_2S]_{Gas, outlet}^{Column} \times \frac{Q_{Biogas}}{V_{Liquid}} + [S-H_2S]_{Gas, outlet}^{Bubble\ column\ reactor} \times \frac{Q_{Air}}{V_{Liquid}} \quad (2)$$

153 S-H₂S removal efficiency (RE):

154
$$RE = \frac{SIL - SER}{SIL} \times 100\% \quad (3)$$

155 S-H₂S elimination capacity (SEC):

156
$$SEC = (SIL - SER) \quad (4)$$

157

158 The sulfur oxidation performance (SOP), defined as the grams of S-SO₄²⁻ produced per
 159 gram of S-H₂S consumed within the desulfurization system, was determined from the
 160 sulfur mass balance taking into account the liquid phase renewal.

161

162 **2.4. Characterization of bacterial communities**

163 Genomic DNA was extracted using PowerSoil[®] DNA isolation kit (MOBIO, USA)
 164 from a biomass sample taken at the end of the desulfurization system operation (day 80)
 165 according to Barragán-Trinidad et al. [24]. The concentration of DNA samples was
 166 quantified by spectrophotometry using a NANODrop 2000c (Thermo Scientific, USA).
 167 DNA samples were submitted to the Research and Testing Laboratory (RTL, Lubbock,
 168 USA) for pyrosequencing analysis using PCR primers 515F
 169 (GTGCCAGCMGCCGCGGTAA) and 806R (GGACTACHVGGGTWTCTAAT) for
 170 bacterial 16S rRNA amplification. Sequences were analyzed using QUIIME software
 171 (Quantitative Insights into Microbial Ecology) according to Caporaso et al. [25] and
 172 selection of operational taxonomic units (OTU) was performed using the UPERASE

173 algorithm [26]. The Chimera searching analysis was performed using the UCHIME
174 software executed in de novo mode [27]. The taxonomic classification of each OTU was
175 performed using its consensus sequence, which was analyzed in RDP classifier and
176 compared with sequences derived from NCBI database.

177

178 **2.5. Analytical procedures**

179 The H₂S and O₂ concentration in gas phase were measured by a certified portable biogas
180 analyzer (GA-m, COMBIMASS[®], Binder, Germany). The inorganic carbon
181 concentration in the liquid phase was determined in a TOC-VCSH analyzer (Shimadzu,
182 Tokyo, Japan). The S-SO₄²⁻ concentration was measured by ion chromatography (883
183 Basic IC Plus, Metrohm, Switzerland). The S²⁻ concentration was measured by
184 potentiometric titration with silver nitrate using the Ag Titrode (848 Titrino plus,
185 Metrohm, Switzerland). The SS and VSS were determined according to Standard
186 Methods [28]. The dissolved oxygen concentration, ORP and conductivity of the liquid
187 phase were measured with specific probes (Cellox[®] 325i, SentixORP, and Cond 340i,
188 respectively, WTW, Germany).

189

190 **3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

191 **3.1. Desulfurization performance**

192 Figure 2a shows the time course of the RE and the SIL of the two-stage desulfurization
193 system. The start-up was carried out by using a SIL of 37 g S m⁻³ h⁻¹, yielding a GRT in
194 the absorption column of 6.6 min (phase A). An average RE value of 94 ± 3% was
195 obtained in this experimental phase, corresponding to a SEC of 35 ± 1 g S m⁻³ h⁻¹. On
196 day 16 (phase B-I), the SIL was increased to 59 g S m⁻³ h⁻¹ by decreasing the GRT to

197 4.1 min, obtaining an average RE value of $82 \pm 3\%$ ($\text{SEC} = 47 \pm 1 \text{ g S m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$). The
198 increase of the liquid velocity from 2.5 to 3.7 m h^{-1} on day 22 (phase B-II) did not
199 improved significantly the H_2S removal performance, reaching an average RE of $85 \pm$
200 2% ($\text{SEC} = 49 \pm 1 \text{ g S m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$). The higher liquid velocity was kept for the rest of the
201 experiment since less sulfur accumulation on the inner surface of the absorption column
202 was observed compared with a velocity of 2.5 m h^{-1} . However, it must be highlighted
203 that sulfur accumulation and detachment was observed on both the absorption column
204 and on the top of the inner surface of the bubble column reactor regardless the liquid
205 velocity tested.

206 <Figure 2>

207

208 The robustness of the desulfurization system to short-term shutdown period was
209 evaluated at day 28 (phase C). After 5 days of a complete operational shutdown (no
210 liquid/gas feed or liquid recirculation), the system was restarted with a SIL of 59 g S m^{-3}
211 h^{-1} and GRT of 4.1 min (phase D). The H_2S removal performance recorded after the
212 short-term shutdown period characterized by average RE and SEC of $85 \pm 8\%$ and $50 \pm$
213 $5 \text{ g S m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$, respectively, was not significantly different than that observed during
214 phase B operation. On day 43, an increase of the SIL to $100 \text{ g S m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ (by reducing the
215 GRT to 2.4 min) was set in order to evaluate the robustness of the desulfurization
216 performance over a sudden change in the operating conditions. It was observed that the
217 system supported a RE of 86% ($\text{SEC} = 86 \text{ g S m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$) 2 hours after the increase of the
218 SIL, which was not significantly different than the RE recorded before the perturbation.
219 Thereafter, the effect of a long-term shutdown period on the H_2S removal performance
220 was investigated. After 18 days of complete operational shutdown, the system was
221 restarted with a SIL of $59 \text{ g S m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ and GRT of 4.1 min. An average RE of $88 \pm 3\%$

222 was recorded since the first day after the long-term shutdown (SEC of $52 \pm 2 \text{ g S m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$
223 ¹, phase F). On day 71, the SIL was increased to $100 \text{ g S m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ by reducing the GRT in
224 the absorption column to 2.4 min, obtaining an average RE of $82 \pm 2\%$ (SEC of $82 \pm 2 \text{ g}$
225 $\text{S m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$). These results confirmed that the two-stage process here proposed was robust
226 to short- and long-term shutdowns and also to sudden operational changes.

227

228 It is important to stress that dissolved oxygen was kept at an average concentration of
229 $8.3 \pm 1.2 \text{ g m}^{-3}$ (Fig. 2b). Such fully aerobic conditions corroborated that the biological
230 process was not limited by oxygen, which is one of the main drawbacks in biofiltration
231 of sulfate-rich biogas [4]. In addition, the average inorganic carbon concentration in the
232 liquid phase was $227 \pm 92 \text{ g C m}^{-3}$, which also granted that the activity of the
233 autotrophic microorganisms was not limited by inorganic carbon (Fig 2b). Moreover,
234 the H_2S concentration recorded at the outlet of the bubble column reactor remained
235 below 3 ppm_v regardless of the experimental condition tested. These negligible values
236 confirmed that no H_2S stripping from the bubble column reactor occurred, and
237 therefore, the treatment technology is safe for potential operators. The O_2 concentration
238 of the purified biogas at the outlet of the absorption column was $1.2 \pm 0.7\%$, showing
239 that the full oxygenation of the liquid phase achieved in the bubble column reactor did
240 not impacted negatively the quality of the purified biogas in terms of O_2 concentration.
241 According to Al-Seadi et al. [29], the O_2 concentration in biogas used in CHP engines,
242 motors and micro-turbines must contain less than $2\% \text{ }_v/v$.

243

244 The relationship between SEC and SIL at the three GRTs tested (6.6, 4.1 and 2.4 min) is
245 shown in Figure 3. The maximum SEC obtained was $82 \pm 2 \text{ g S m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ (SIL of 100 g C
246 $\text{m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$, GRT= 2.4 min). Most studies on desulfurization of H_2S -rich biogas under fully

247 aerobic conditions were performed with biotrickling filters. Although biotrickling filters
248 treating SIL values in the range of 23–348 g S m⁻³ h⁻¹ and GRTs of 0.55–9.66 min can
249 be found in the literature [6,15], the most common GRTs for biotrickling filters are in
250 the range of 1.66–3.33 min [9,30,31]. At comparable SIL and GRT than that tested in
251 the present study, Aita et al. [4] found REs ranging from 49 to 97% (SIL= 163 g S m⁻³
252 h⁻¹, GRT = 2.82 min) and Montebello et al. [15] obtained nearly complete H₂S removal
253 with SIL of 100 g S m⁻³ h⁻¹ (GRT =2.16–1.25 min). Chaiprapat et al. [9] obtained a RE=
254 89.0 ± 6.8% and RE=80.1 ± 10.2% in a triple stage and single stage biotrickling filter
255 (SIL = 184 ± 45 g S m⁻³ h⁻¹, GRT = 3 min). It is noticeable that elemental sulfur
256 accumulation on the packing material of the biotrickling filters is a common
257 phenomenon, leading to operational problems such overpressure and clogging [6,23].
258 The bioscrubber achieved outlet H₂S concentrations ≤ 500 ppm_v only at the gas
259 residence time of 6.6 min. At gas residence times of 4.1 and 2.4 min the outlet H₂S
260 concentrations were 750 and 900 ppm_v, respectively. Therefore, further optimization is
261 required. Since biomass in the system was not retained in a packing material, the
262 maximum biomass residence time coincided with the hydraulic retention time.
263 Therefore, biomass carriers could be added into the bubble column reactor to increase
264 the biomass residence time. This strategy might result in a reduced sulphide
265 concentration in liquid phase and improved H₂S absorption at gas residence times
266 shorter than 6.6 min.

267 <Figure 3>

268

269 Several authors have demonstrated that separating the H₂S absorption and the biological
270 oxidation processes allows a more efficient desulfurization performance when dealing
271 with H₂S-rich biogas [9,21,30]. Thus, the biological oxidation module can be

272 independently aerated, which maintains fully aerobic conditions in the liquid phase and
273 avoids accumulation of elemental sulfur. However, these previous studies lacked of (i) a
274 detailed characterization of the air leaving the biological oxidation module, (ii) a
275 detailed characterization of the sulfur species in the liquid phase and the oxidation
276 performance, or used a sophisticated oxidation module such as an airlift bioreactor. In
277 the present study, it was confirmed that a relatively simple configuration based on
278 coupling an absorption column with a bubble column can achieve high, robust and
279 stable H₂S removal. It was also confirmed that no significant H₂S stripping occurred
280 from the oxidation module, while the purified biogas was not significantly enriched
281 with O₂ in the absorption column. Moreover, in the present system high H₂S removal
282 and oxidation performance were reached with low liquid velocities in the absorption
283 column, being up to 2.7-5 times lower than liquid velocities previously reported in
284 aerobic biotrickling filters [14,31]. It is worth noting that in the present study a
285 relatively simple bubble column was used as an aerated bioreaction module, which is
286 significantly different from the airlift bioreactor used in our previous proof-of-concept
287 study [21]. This difference is remarkable towards upgrading former desulfurization
288 facilities based on chemical absorption. The implementation of a bubble column is
289 easier than the airlift bioreactor and practically any liquid container can be used as a
290 bubble column. Moreover, the present two-stage bioscrubber was operated under more
291 interesting gas residence times from an applied point of view (e.g. 2.4 to 6.6 min), the
292 additional respirometric studies and the measurements of sulphides in liquid phase
293 confirmed the high oxidation performance of the enriched microbial community (see
294 Section 3.2).

295

296 **3.2. Sulfur oxidation performance**

297 The fully aerobic conditions in the bubble column reactor resulted in a high oxidation
298 performance, achieving an average SOP of $91 \pm 10\%$ after 48 h of operation (Fig. 4a). It
299 was observed that sulfur was quickly accumulated on the inner surface of the absorption
300 column and at the top of the bubble column reactor. The low O_2 concentration in the gas
301 phase ($< 2\%$, resulting from the gas/liquid contact) and the recirculation of the culture
302 broth from the bubble column reactor led to the formation of a small film containing
303 elemental sulfur on the walls of the absorption column. The sporadic detachment and
304 introduction of this film into the bubble column reactor produced SOP values higher
305 than 100%. Respirometric tests were periodically performed in order to confirm that the
306 oxygen uptake rate (OUR) correlated with the oxygen uptake required to achieve the
307 SEC recorded. Figure 4b shows the OUR estimated from the SEC values by assuming
308 that all the H_2S removed was converted into sulfate (2 mole of O_2 per mole of H_2S). It
309 was observed that the OUR determined experimentally correlated well with the
310 estimated values from SEC, supporting a R^2 coefficient of 0.88. On day 72, with the
311 increase of the SIL up to $100 \text{ g S m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$, the resulting SOP was $95 \pm 14\%$. The high
312 SOP values achieved during the whole experimental time demonstrated the capability of
313 the system to fully oxidize most sulfur removed in the absorption column. The
314 maximum sulfate concentration reached in the liquid phase was above $25,000 \text{ g m}^{-3}$
315 (Fig. 5a). This high sulfate concentration together with the dilution rates of 5.7×10^{-3} –
316 $8.6 \times 10^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ and the slightly alkaline conditions set in the system certainly promoted the
317 selection of a specialized microbial community within the bubble column reactor.
318 Interestingly, the maximum S^{2-} concentration measured in the liquid phase was $\sim 29 \text{ g m}^{-3}$
319 3 , with an average concentration of $11.6 \pm 5.2 \text{ g m}^{-3}$ (Fig 5b). This negligible S^{2-}
320 concentration (~ 1000 times lower than sulfate concentration) also confirmed that

321 microbial sulfur oxidation was highly efficient in the bioscrubber with the preferential
322 formation of sulfate.

323 <Figure 4>

324 <Figure 5>

325

326 The high sulfur oxidation performance of the bioscrubber was achieved with an average
327 biomass concentration of 201.4 ± 110.2 mg VSS m^{-3} . Even when a relatively low
328 biomass concentration was determined in the liquid phase, the microbial community
329 was resilient towards shutdown periods without liquid/gas feed or liquid recirculation.
330 The system required only 2 days to recover SOP values higher than 80% after restarting
331 the system from short- and long-term shutdowns, respectively. The oxidation
332 performance recorded in the bioscrubber was also consistent with the ORP values
333 recorded, which ranged from 50 to 130 mV throughout the whole experiment. This
334 parameter can be directly related with the oxidant potential and with the metabolites of
335 the system. ORP values from -100 mV and above indicated the predominant presence of
336 SO_4^{2-} in desulfurization processes [8,32]. Likewise, Fortuny et al. [6] pointed out that
337 ORP values ranging from -250 to -400 mV are related with the oxidation of S^{2-} to S^0 .

338

339 The main products of biotrickling filters treating H_2S are usually elemental sulfur and
340 sulfate, being the elemental sulfur/sulfate ratio dependent on the experimental
341 conditions such as the relationship between O_2 and H_2S and the liquid velocity [6,9,14].
342 Fortuny et al. [6] obtained a SOP of 60-70% at an inlet load of 3,000 ppm_v, while the
343 SOP decreased up to 20-30% when the H_2S inlet concentration was increased to 6,000
344 ppm_v due to the oxygen limitation. Montebello et al. [15] found a decrease on the SOP
345 from ~100% to ~50% with the increase of SIL from 52 to 263 g S $m^{-3} h^{-1}$ (GRT=2.16

346 min). The liquid velocity is a key parameter related with the availability of oxygen and
347 H₂S absorption performance in biotrickling filters [9,14]. In some cases, biotrickling
348 filters require liquid velocities between 4.4 and 18.9 m h⁻¹ to achieved SOPs higher than
349 70% [14]. The configuration here proposed supported stable SOP values through the
350 experiment with a relatively low liquid velocity, which is an advantage in terms of
351 economic feasibility of the process [21]. Therefore, the bioreactor configuration here
352 developed is a good alternative to conventional desulfurization technologies when
353 dealing with H₂S-rich biogas.

354

355 **3.3. Characterization of bacterial communities**

356 The characterization of the microbial communities was carried out at the end of the
357 experiment to identify the most abundant species in the system after 80 days of
358 operation. In the present study prevailed (i) fully aerobic conditions, (ii) slightly alkaline
359 conditions and (iii) sulfate concentrations in the liquid phase of up to 25,000 g m⁻³. Such
360 conditions are not common in desulfurization processes, and therefore, the
361 characterization of the resulting microbial community was relevant for understanding
362 the performance of the system. An overview of the microbial populations is presented in
363 Figure 6, while the specific bacteria with relative abundances higher than 1% are
364 presented in Table 2. All bacterial populations and their relative abundances are given in
365 Table S1 (Supplementary material). It was clearly observed that the predominant
366 phylum was *Proteobacteria* with a relative abundance of 90.8%. Two main classes of
367 *Proteobacteria* were found: *Gammaproteobacteria* and *Alphaproteobacteria*, with a
368 relative abundance of 69.7% and 21.1%, respectively. Among *Gammaproteobacteria*,
369 *Thioalkalimicrobium cyclicum* was the most abundant specie with a relative abundance
370 of 68.2%, while only the 1.5% belonged to the order of *Xanthomonadales* (family,

371 genus and specie not identified). Regarding the *Alphaproteobacteria*, the identified
372 species were *Stappia sp* (13.5%) and *Ochrobactrum sp* (7.6%). The bioreactor was
373 inoculated with activated sludge due to its high content in sulfur oxidizing communities
374 widely reported in the literature [13,33–35].

375

376 The most abundant bacteria in the present study was *Thioalkalimicrobium cyclicum*, a
377 sulfur-oxidizing bacteria obligately chemolithotrophic, alkaliphilic and moderately
378 halophilic with optimum pH ranging from 7.5 to 10.5 [36]. This bacterium has been
379 highlighted for its ability to oxidize sulfide and thiosulphate to sulfate without elemental
380 sulfur formation [36,37]. In addition, this bacterium grows well in saline environments
381 (e.g. media with 1.3 M of Na⁺) [38], which agrees with the high sulfate concentration
382 reached in the present study. *Thioalkalimicrobium* has been previously reported in
383 systems of desulfurization of H₂S-rich biogas. Recently, Quijano et al. [21] found an
384 increase of 5.59% on the relative abundance of this bacteria after 46 days treating
385 concentrations of biogas of 2,500-10,000 ppm_v. Likewise, the *Alphaproteobacteria*
386 *Stappia sp.* has been associated with the conversion of sulfide to elemental sulfur [39],
387 while *Ochrobactrum sp.* can oxidize the elemental sulfur to sulphate [39] or directly
388 produce sulphate from sulfide or thiosulphate [40]. Hence, the particular operating
389 conditions of the present work resulted in a microbial ecosystem highly specialized for
390 the full oxidation of H₂S to sulfate.

391 <Figure 6>

392 <Table 2>

393

394 **4. Conclusions**

395 This study demonstrated the technical feasibility of a fully aerobic bioscrubber for the
396 desulfurization of H₂S-rich biogas. Typical operating problems in biotrickling filters
397 such as packed bed clogging (due to elemental sulfur accumulation) or biogas dilution
398 are avoided in the present system. Moreover, the main end-product of the process was
399 sulfate, which can be readily valorized for fertilizer production. It was observed that no
400 significant H₂S stripping occurred from the aerated bioreactor, which confirmed the
401 safety of the desulfurization process for potential operators. The bioscrubber was also
402 robust and resilient towards short- and long-term operation shutdowns, which are prone
403 to occur in industrial scenarios. The operating conditions of the process led to the
404 enrichment of a highly specialized bacterial community, being *Thioalkalimicrobium*
405 *cyclicum* the most abundant one. Based on the high and stable H₂S removal efficiency,
406 the high sulfur oxidation performance and the competitive GRTs used in this study, this
407 novel desulfurization system is a promising technology for the treatment of H₂S-rich
408 biogas.

409

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418

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556 **Figure captions**

557 **Fig. 1.** Schematic representation of the desulfurization system.

558 **Fig. 2.** Time course of (a) H₂S removal efficiency (RE, %) of the bioscrubber under
559 several sulfur inlet loads (SIL, g S m_{liquid}⁻³ h⁻¹), and (b) Dissolved oxygen (DO) and
560 inorganic carbon (IC) concentrations.

561 **Fig. 3.** Characteristic SEC vs SIL curve of the fully aerobic scrubber.

562 **Fig. 4.** Time course of (a) sulfur oxidation performance (SOP, %), and (b) oxygen
563 uptake rate (OUR, g O₂ m_{liquid}⁻³ h⁻¹) where: OUR estimated from SEC values (squares)
564 and experimental OUR values from respirometric tests (circles).

565 **Fig 5.** Time course of (a) SO₄²⁻ concentration, and (b) S²⁻ concentration in the liquid
566 phase.

567 **Fig. 6.** Overview of the bacterial communities present in the bioscrubber after 80 days
568 of operation and their relative abundances determined by 16S rRNA pyrosequencing.

Table 1. Summary of the experimental conditions tested in the bioscrubber.

Phase	Days	SIL ($\text{g S m}^{-3} \text{h}^{-1}$)	GRT (min)	V_L (m h^{-1})
A	0-15	37	6.6	2.5
B-I	16-21	59	4.1	2.5
B-II	21-27	59	4.1	3.7
C	28-32	0	0.0	0
D	33-43	59	4.1	3.7
E	44-61	0	0.0	0
F	62-71	59	4.1	3.7
G	71-79	100	2.4	3.7

Table 2. Predominant bacteria identified in the bioscrubber at day 80 under steady conditions.

Phylum	Class	Order	Family	Genus	Specie	Relative abundance (%)
<i>Proteobacteria</i>	<i>Gammaproteobacteria</i>	<i>Thiotrichales</i>	<i>Piscirickettsiaceae</i>	<i>Thioalkalimicrobium</i>	<i>Thioalkalimicrobium cyclicum</i>	68.18
<i>Proteobacteria</i>	<i>Gammaproteobacteria</i>	<i>Xanthomonadales</i>	<i>Unclassified</i>	<i>Unclassified</i>	<i>Unclassified</i>	1.51
<i>Proteobacteria</i>	<i>Alphaproteobacteria</i>	<i>Rhodobacterales</i>	<i>Rhodobacteraceae</i>	<i>Stappia</i>	<i>Stappia sp</i>	13.49
<i>Proteobacteria</i>	<i>Alphaproteobacteria</i>	<i>Rhizobiales</i>	<i>Brucellaceae</i>	<i>Ochrobactrum</i>	<i>Ochrobactrum sp</i>	7.61

Fig. 1.

Fig. 2.

Fig.3

Fig. 4.

Fig. 5.

Fig. 6.

